

STUDY OF THE PROPERTY OF LIGHTWEIGHT BUILDING STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

GFRP panels have been increasingly used for structural applications due to its light weight, corrosion resistance and construction-easiness and other advantages it offers over conventional material. As the building codes require, it is very unlikely that maximum wind followed by maximum earthquake activity, engineers have to design structures for the maximum load which is always caused by both wind or seismic. This paper presents a comparative study to evaluates the seismic and wind performance of GFRP wall panel into a multi-storey building primary design based on Finite Element Analysis and numerical calculations. The GFRP panels are designed to replace traditional concrete wall in multi-storey building. The proposed building is situated at earthquake zone VI, which has floor plan dimension 11.4m by 44.4m and height 6 storey each with storey height of 3m summing up to a total height of 18m. A total of 4 buildings were modelled and tested, FEA analysis of the models are carried out using the Chinese Standards Codes and supported by finite element analysis software Ansys, which is one of the famous and most widely used analyses software in civil engineering structures in both practical and research applications. Comparisons of the models are then made between wind and seismic performance of building with GFRP wall panels in conventional RC building in terms of storey displacements and stresses are presented which helped to find the various analytical properties of the both structures and also have a very systematic design for the structure. The results validations indicated that either software application could be used for the parametric study.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of FRPs as a construction material has increased in recent years, primarily because of the non-corrosive nature and high tensile strength of the material. In the past decades, FRP composites have gained acceptance and are growing in popularity in civil infrastructure applications due to their favourable characteristics. FRP composites have lightweight, non-corrosive, non-magnetic, and non-conductive properties, a high fatigue life and are extremely durable. They exhibit excellent thermal insulation and energy absorption characteristics in addition to their high strength. In spite of such excellent mechanical properties, the use of FRP in civil engineering has been limited to strengthening or rehabilitating existing structural components because of the expensive cost of the materials[1].

Early researchers Clarke [2] and Davalos et al. [3] mainly focused on the static behavior of FRP, there has been some recent studies on their dynamic behaviour through analytical and experimental investigations [4, 5]. For instance, Mosallam et al. [6] carried out a comprehensive study on the pultruded GFRP beam-to-column connections under both static and dynamic loads, concluding that GFRP connections could be modeled as semi-rigid in frame analysis. Russo [7] used free vibration response to identify its structural information including fundamental frequencies, mode shapes and damping coefficients of a large FRP space frame. Yang et al. [8] researched into the dynamic and fatigue performances of a pultruded FRP frame, concluding that there was no significant degradation of FRP components after 2.1 million cycles of fatigue load. Bai and Keller [9] studied the dynamic

structural response using output only identification techniques under impact and human walking excitations of an all-FRP pedestrian bridge. Recently, Ding et al. [10] applied a constant axial load and a cyclic lateral load to achieved satisfactory seismic performance of composite frames. While all these researches represent pioneer work in fostering the understanding of the dynamic behavior of FRP components, to the best of the authors' knowledge, wind and seismic behavior of FRP panels as load-bearing walls need to be studied.

FRP panels in previous years, were mainly designed for bridge decks and building floors slabs. For example, GFRP deck panel with rectangular holes filled with foam was proposed to improve deck strength and stiffness Zi et al. [11]. Satisivam et al. [12] conducted research on modular FRP sandwich panels for building floors, which composed of FRP pultruded boxes bonded with two GFRP plates. The authors indicated that foam filling, adhesive bonding, and bidirectional pultrusion orientation improved the flexural load-bearing capacity of the panels. The FRP sandwich panels could also be bolted to steel beams to form a composite beam and slab systems. Hao et al. [13] studied seismic performance of GFRP wall panels based on comprehensive shaking table tests and Finite Element Analysis; it was demonstrated that GFRP wall panels cannot replace RC walls in multi-story buildings due to their low stiffness, their performances are comparable to RC walls for low-rise buildings. Comprehensive research on the seismic and wind performance of RC walls has been conducted experimentally [14-16] and numerically [17]. The inelastic seismic response of RC walls is complex because it includes multiple vibration modes in the nonlinear range, the post-elastic behavior of concrete and steel under dynamic loading, and the interactions among flexural, shear, and axial cyclic loadings. FRP wall panels have huge advantages over to traditional RC walls. Due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, easy application, and resistance to corrosion, FRP materials have been used to enhance strength and ductility of the existing structural walls [18]. However, in contrast to RC walls, FRP wall panels do not yield and have relatively low stiffness. A question arises whether FRP panels are suitable for seismic and wind reduction, and how their performance would compare with RC walls.

The above background necessitates much more research to develop a better understanding on the behavior of RC and FRP composite buildings subjected to lateral loads. In this study, the authors investigate RC and glass fiber walls panels and as structural walls, the models are developed in ANSYS where wind and seismic loading capacity of FRP composite and RC walls are of interest. A total of 4 buildings were modelled and tested, among which 2 specimens were subjected to seismic loads and the other 2 specimens subjected to wind loads. GFP wall panels are design to replace traditional RC shear wall in FRP composite structure; it is a non-load bearing wall which can resist lateral loads applied to the surface and support their own weight. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes constitutive theory of materials for the analysis of FRP composite and RC building in Ansys software. Section 3 reports the building description and various forces exposed to RC building using numerical analysis. Section 4 describes finite element analysis of FRP composite and RC buildings in Ansys software the results from the analysis were compared under. Section 5 concludes the by discussing the results and potential applications of RC and GFRP structures.

2 CONSTITUTIVE THEORY OF MATERIALS FOR RC AND FRP BUILDINGS

2.1 Laminate composite for composite

A single lamina of the FRP sheet consists of unidirectional fibers embedded in the matrix, which is taken as a transversely isotropic material in modelling the plane normal to the fiber direction. In the plane stress state, the stress-strain relationship of lamina in the local coordinate (*i.e.*, 1, 2 and 3) and in the structure coordinate (x , y and z) can be respectively expressed, as follows:

$$\sigma_1 = Q_{e1} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma = \bar{Q}_e \quad (1\text{?})$$

$$\bar{Q} = T^{-1}QT^{-T} \quad (3)$$

where T indicates the transformation matrix; the σ and ε are for the stress and strain vectors in the local coordinate (x , y , and z), respectively; while the σ and ε_1 are for the stress and strain vectors in the structure coordinate (1, 2, and 3), respectively. Simultaneously, the coefficients of the constitutive matrix Q can be rendered as follows:

$$Q_{11} = E_1 / \eta_{12}, Q_{12} = Q_{21} = E_2 \nu_{12} / \eta_{12}, Q_{22} = E_2 / \eta_{12}, Q_{33} = G_{12}, \eta_{12} = 1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21} \quad (4)$$

where E_1 is for the modulus of the lamina in the fiber direction; E_2 for the modulus normal to the fiber direction; ν_{ij} for the Poisson's ratio for the deformation in the j direction in loading in the i direction; and G_{12} for the in-plane shear modulus of the lamina.

Figure 1: Thin plate and its coordinates

From the constitutive equation for a single lamina, the in-plane stress-strain relation of a laminated composite can be an equivalent orthotropic composite material in the coordinate (x , y , and z).

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1}) = \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k t_k \quad (5)$$

where n is for the total number of plies; t_k the thickness of the k layer and the z -coordinate of its centerline and h_k for the distance from the mid-plane of the lamina to each ply. In applying to concrete structural beam or column members, a combination of the FRP sheet and concrete can refine the innovated strength and deformation capacity of the structure. The components of displacement in the x -, y -, and z - directions in fig 1 is often denoted by u , v , and w . The strain is the change in length divided by the original length, which gives the strain components in the three directions.

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}; \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}; \varepsilon_z = \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \quad (6)$$

and the components of shear strain:

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} - 2z \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (7)$$

Each of these ply stresses must add to balance the traction per unit width N ; the mean internal force N acting on the upper composite plate with unit width are defined as:

$$N = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \sigma dz = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \sigma_k dz \quad (8)$$

where σ_k is the stress in the k th ply and Z_k is the distance from the laminate midplane to the bottom of the k th ply.

3 BUILDING DESCRIPTION

The structure used in this study is two multi-storey building models are designed and seismic and wind responses are assessed and compared, the basic planning and the loading conditions are considered the same for both building structures. The structural members for RC structure are considered reinforced concrete and designed as per the Chinese code [19], in case of FRP composite structure, the walls are considered GFRP composite but beam, column and slab remain reinforced concrete. The building considered has six stories planned to facilitate the basic requirements of a residential building. The building is assumed to be situated in Dalian, China which is located at seismic activity zone VI. The total height of the building is kept at 18 meters; each floor has a height of 3 meters. The building has two units and two depths of 5.1 meters and 6.3 meter respectively. The length of the building is 44.4 meters and width are 11.4 meters, additional dimensions of the building is presented in table 1. Columns are taken to be square, as the square columns are more suitable for earthquake resistant structures. The study is carried on the same building plan for FRP composite building with the same basic assumptions made for deciding preliminary sections of both the structures. The basic loading on both types of structures is kept the same. Fig.2 and Fig. 3 shows the floor plan and elevation view of the building respectively.

Figure 2: Plan of the model.

3.2 Wind load

The surface pressure acting on a building is usually described by pressure coefficients, calculated through normalisation with the velocity pressure in the undisturbed approaching wind at reference height, which is often chosen as the height of the building. The national basic wind pressure distribution; w_k is standard value of wind loads perpendicular to the surface of a building.

$$w_k = \beta_z \mu_s \mu_z w_0 \quad (9)$$

where μ_s represents aerodynamic pressure coefficient, $\mu_s = 0.3$, the total height of the building is 18 meters ground roughness selected is class C, $\gamma = 0.4$ basic self-vibration period of frame structure $T = 0.63s$. μ_z is pressure exposure factor. β_z represents dynamic response factor at the height of Z ; the basic wind pressure w_0 is basic self-oscillation period T of frame structure and surface roughness.

Figure 3: Elevation view

Details	Dimensions
Plan dimension	11.4m×44.4m
Total height	18m
Number of stories	6
Internal wall	0.20 m
External wall	0.30 m
Slab thickness	0.15 m
beam	0.25m × 0.50 m
Column	0.50m × 0.50 m
Concrete	C30
Seismic zone	GB50011-2010
Wind load	GB50009-2012

Figure 1: Dimensions of the building

3.3 Seismic loading

Seismic load calculations and application procedures are within the guidelines and scope of Chinese seismic standard [20], the project considered is situated at site class II of 6 degree of seismic precautionary intensity, to calculate for seismic action, gravitational load of the building structure represents the permanent load standard value and the sum of variable load combination values. The variable load combination value coefficient is used as follows; Snow loads 0.5, Floor live load by the equivalent of live load calculation according to civil building choose 0.5, excluding roof live load. In actual calculation of seismic action under each column shear force, gravity load value of the entire buildings is calculated as a whole, thus calculating total shear force of building layers, the total shear stiffness of each layer is then distributed to each column. Earthquake impact coefficient.

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{T_g}{T} \right)^\gamma \eta_2 \alpha_{\max} \quad (10)$$

where, α_{\max} = maximum value of seismic influence coefficient 6-degree area of frequent earthquake chooses 0.04 ; T_g is the characteristic period, if the design earthquake group is group 1,

choose 0.35 for site class II. T is natural vibration period of structure chooses 0.53; r is attenuation index, $n =$ is damping adjustment coefficient. When base shear force method is used, only one degree of freedom may be considered for each story and the building height should not exceed 40mm; stiffness and mass are evenly distributed along height direction. This height of the building is 18.09m, but can still be calculated using this method.

$$F_i = \frac{G_i H_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n G_j H_j} F_{EK} (1 - \delta_n) \quad (11)$$

where F_{EK} - standard value of total horizontal earthquake action of a structure,

$$F_{EK} = \alpha G_{eq} \quad (12)$$

α_1 - value of horizontal seismic influence of coefficient corresponding to basic natural vibration period of structure. The characteristic value of vertical seismic action shall be determined by the following equations equation 4. The effects of vertical seismic action at floor level may be distributed in proportion of representative value of gravity load acting on the members, which should multiply with the amplified factor.

$$F_i = \left(\frac{H_i G_i}{\sum H_i G_i} \right) \times F_{EK} \quad (13)$$

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS SIMULATION OF BUILDING MODELS TEST

Many finite element analysis programs are available to predict the structural behavior of multi-story building walls subjected to different loading actions, and ANSYS is one of them. ANSYS has been successfully used by many researchers in the nonlinear analyses and strength predictions of building frames and claddings. It will provide accurate results for both RC and FRP wall panel provided their loading and boundary conditions and mechanical properties are modelled accurately. This research is aimed at determining the structural analysis and behavior of the comparative study of RC and FRP building when subjected to various load levels under wind and seismic actions. This section presents the details of finite element modelling of both building models. FE study has been performed considering various parameters such as the geometry of the entire building, material properties of the model as presented in table 2 and details of confining elements.

Property	Concrete	Glass fiber	steel
Density (kg/m ³)	2500	2000	7800
Young's modulus (GPa)	3×10 ⁴	7.2×10 ⁴	3×10 ⁵
Poisson's ratio (v)	0.2	0.294	0.3
Gravitational acceleration(g/m×s ⁻²)	9.8	9.8	9.8

Table 2: Material properties

4.1 Element type, boundary conditions, mesh and loads

FEA models are constructed using Ansys (v14.5). Shell281 element is used to simulate GFRP wall panel, RC wall and floor slab. The walls are considered to be non-load bearing but they resist wind load applied to the façade and also support their own weight and cladding. BEAM188 element is used

to simulate beam and column. Both are modelled as two noded beam elements in 3d with six degree of freedom at each node. All columns are interconnected by grade beams at finished ground level.

In terms of boundary conditions, the bottom of the building models was assumed as fully constrained to prevent movement of the entire building models when lateral forces are applied as shown in Fig. 4.

To obtain a good mesh results from both BEAM188 and SHELL281 elements, the software meshes the components into small elements in order to increase the accuracy of the analysis. The building model in this study consists of beam, column slab and shear wall. The mesh size chosen for shell element is 30mm×30mm. The mesh size of beam element should be the same as the size of the shell element unit in the same direction. The top and bottom meshes intersect with the shear wall meshes forming the complete model.

The developed FE models were subjected to different kinds of actions. The structural system must resist both vertical and lateral loads. Different loads are listed below. To determine wind forces acting on the building models, the wind pressure is applied horizontally to the surface of the walls of each layer, the proper way to apply wind loads on finite element model is as a linear force on elements. The seismic load is applied by taking acceleration [20], the coefficient code is combined with seismic force, which is applied horizontally to the building joints. Live load is applied in the form of pressure to each layer of the floors. The self-weight from structural members, non-structural members and from installations, self-weight is applied to the corresponding structure in the form of gravity. Table 3 depicts weight comparison of RC and FRP composite structure.

Figure 4: Boundary condition applied to entire modeling

Type of structure	Density (Kg/m ³)	Volume	Self-weight (kg)
RC	2500	991.907	2,479,767.5
FRP composite	2000	258.930 474.047	1,702,977.5

Table 3: Weight comparison of reinforced concrete and FRP composite structure

4.2 Comparison of stresses in FRP composite and RC walls under wind and seismic loads

The variation of stresses in FRP composite and RC walls are shown in Fig 5 to Fig 9. As per the stress results presented in Fig.5 demonstrated that the GFRP panel remained elastic under seismic actions Fig. 5(a) and (b). In order to further evaluate the performance of GFRP wall panel under seismic excitations, its performance is compared with RC walls under the same seismic conditions with the same thickness. It was originally used as a control specimen. The maximum stress of the

Figure 5: Stress of FRP composite and RC walls under seismic loads (a)FRP external wall (b) FRP internal wall (c) RC external wall (d) RC internal wall.

Figure 6: Von Mises stress of FRP composite walls (a) external (b) internal

GFRP panel appears in internal walls Fig. 5(b). The largest stress in RC building, as expected, appears in between first and third floor, as presented in Fig. 5(d). Fig. 6 displays the von Mises stress contours of FRP composite walls, external and internal, respectively under wind loads. As can be seen, the

internal wall as illustrated in Fig. 6(b) was found to have developed maximum stress obtained at the corner of the last floor as compared to that of the external wall. Meanwhile, the maximum stress of external wall Fig. 6(a) appeared at the front view of the second layer of FRP wall. It should note that the stress along the global x-axis is located at the bottom of the beams sections i.e. ground floor slab, while for the rest of the locations that are located at vertical structural members which are columns and walls, the z-axis stress was chosen to be graphically visualized.

Figure 7: Stress of FRP composite and RC walls under wind loads (a)FRP external wall (b) FRP internal wall (c) RC external wall (d) RC internal wall.

Figure 7: show a comparative analysis of stress distribution in building models under wind loading. For each model, it can be seen from the results that the stress in the walls of both models are almost identical; this implies that FRP and RC walls perform almost equal under wind loading. Figure 7(b) shows that the stress distribution in the external wall of FRP composite is higher whereas lower in RC building model and vice versa in internal walls.

4.3 Comparison of displacement in FRP composite and RC walls under wind and seismic loads

Figure 8 depicts a comparison of displacement between the FRP composite and RC walls under wind loads for all two building models in x and y directions. It is noticed from the results of wind and seismic are either similar or almost identical. The results of analysis revealed that in FRP composite, there is maximum displacement and minimum in RC building with respect to the storey height of both building structures when subjected to wind loads, it is higher than the displacement values for earthquake.

Figure 8: Comparison of story displacement in walls under wind loads.

Figure 9: Comparison of story displacement in walls under seismic loads.

Comparing values of both buildings RC structure is nearly double than that of FRP composite but within a permissible limit. Figure 9 shows that the displacement caused by the earthquake on the structures tends to gradually increases due to increase in the story level. It is observed that in the case of building with RC the maximum story displacement is lower but double in FRP composite but within the limit.

From the above results, it can be concluded that the FEA models of both RC and GFRP walls are presented. To gain a better understanding of the FRP wall panel's ability to resist wind and seismic loads, a comparison of FRP wall panel and RC wall is carried out by simulating the responses of both types of walls under earthquake and wind actions. FRP walls are able to withstand bigger displacements as compared to RC walls.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Form the analysis of results of a numerical study on RC and FRP composite walls for multi-story housing subjected to wind and seismic actions, the following conclusions can be drawn: FRP composite has the maximum displacement when subjected to both wind and seismic loads, this implies that FRP composite exhibits good resistance to both wind and earthquake loads due to its high strength

and lightweight characteristics; it's also had a potential to be used as seismic-resistant structural walls. After comparing the stress results and the performances of both building models under seismic loads, we can conclude that, in multi-story buildings, RC walls are able to withstand high stresses as compared to FRP walls. Hence, RC walls remain a better option. Wind loading comparative analysis of stress distribution in FRP and RC walls revealed that both models performed almost equal. However, when FRP composite walls are designed to replace traditional walls in low-rise buildings, the maximum stress of RC and FRP walls will be closer compared to those for multi-story buildings. Moreover, FRP walls has low self-weight and high strength and extremely easier for post-earthquake repair and replacement, which makes FRP walls a workable solution for low-rise buildings in seismic zones.

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